

FORMATION OF COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENT IN MODERN
BANKS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the role of monopolistic bank competition in the market economy, its positive and negative consequences, the need to fight against it, and the work carried out in this regard in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords. *Market economy, business, bank, competition, monopoly, price, service, profit, economy.*

Competition is also divided into fair and honorable competition in terms of choosing the way of struggle. Fair competition is conducted in the accepted and acceptable ways in the market, based on the rules of the market. Unfair competition involves the use of prohibited and prohibited methods, such as fraud, deceit, dishonesty, deception, economic espionage, subversion, and even physical violence. A market economy actually recognizes only fair competition. Competition keeps the economy healthy.

Free competition includes any legal methods of acquiring and maintaining customers that are not related to lowering prices (increasing quality, extending service life, environmental cleanliness, safety, etc.) According to the Decree "On additional measures to reduce state participation", the creation of a competitive environment in the market of modern banking services was determined at a very high level.

According to the law, some reasons are indicated as negative factors for creating a healthy competitive environment in banking services:

- ✓ too much state dominance in the economy;
- ✓ excessive regulation of prices;
- ✓ regulation of privileges and preferences;
- ✓ high regulatory burden on business entities and lack of interest of industry regulatory bodies in development of competition;
- ✓ -abuse of natural monopoly;
- ✓ lack of improvement of legal mechanisms to combat anti-competitive situations.

Foreign experience shows that commercial banks that provide higher quality services to their clients definitely have an advantage over banks with a limited range of services. Recently, large commercial banks are moving to comprehensive customer service. This means that in addition to credit settlement and cashier services, banks provide their customers with a whole range of other services.

As a result of the ongoing reforms, market mechanisms of service provision are being introduced in the banking system, their types are expanding, and financial openness is increasing for entrepreneurs and residents.

First of all, banks fully take over accounting and accounting services for customers, that is, keeping depreciation and pension accounts, accounting operations, calculating and paying taxes, calculating wages, monitoring the dynamics of warehouse stocks, selling and analysis of operating costs, regulation of project investment balance. and consolidated balance sheets for companies.

Secondly, an important direction in the development of relations between large companies and banks is the transfer of the responsibility for keeping documents to the latter, and in recent years, information on the movement of settlement documents has been published daily, weekly and monthly balances.

delivery of information. Carrying out banking operations with a wide range of customers is an important feature of modern banking in all countries of the world with a developed banking system. For example, the largest commercial banks of Great Britain (clearing banks) perform about 100 types of operations to serve their customers, commercial banks in the USA - more than 150 types of operations, and Japanese banks - about 300 types.

In modern conditions, the role of banks controlled by foreign capital is increasing in the market of banking services in Europe with a transformational economy (banks with more than 50% of the charter capital owned by non-residents). Some researchers are trying to assess how the presence of these banks affects the public's attitude towards the banking system as a whole. They compare trends in transition economies in Central and Eastern Europe. Although competition seems unsystematic, it is based on a certain strategy to protect the interests of market participants.

In order to have a clear idea about competition, it is necessary to dwell on the concept of "competition" first. It is worth mentioning that for a long time the concept of "competition" has meant the independent struggle of two or more individuals (competitors) who are interested in obtaining the maximum profit. Competition performs a number of important functions. Among them, the most important ones are determining and determining the market value of goods and services in society, turning certain work into necessary work for society.

Due to competition, equalization of individual values and, accordingly, differentiation of profits based on differences in organizational management and labor productivity occurs. Competition forms the average rate of profit from the point of view of inter-sectors, leads to the flow of capital in favor of the sectors needed by the society. Competition undoubtedly works in the market's favor by determining when, what and how many goods and services it is appropriate to offer and develop.

The concept of "competition" is the most important and widely used concept in classical and neoclassical economic theory, and it attracts the serious and constant attention of many economists and is interpreted by them in different ways. There are three different approaches to its description in the literature devoted to competition problems. The first approach describes competition as competition in the market. The second approach, characteristic of classical economic theory, considers competition as an element of the market mechanism that balances supply and demand. The third approach is based on the modern theory of market understanding and considers competition as a category that defines the types of network market.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Restriction of Monopolistic Activity in Commodity Markets and Competition", "competition is the competition of economic entities, in which their independent actions by each entity in the respective commodity market limits the possibility of influencing the general conditions of goods circulation¹". In this law, it is determined that competition applies only to commodity markets.

References

1. Muhammedrizaevna, T. M., Khakimovna, U. M., Abdullayevna, K. Z., & Bayazovna, G. N. The Role Of Using Innovations In Improving The Competitiveness Of Goods. *Gwalior Management Academy*, 11.
2. Gafurova, S. K. (2023). Quality Management In Education: A Systematic Approach. *Educational Research In Universal Sciences*, 2(17), 126-129.
3. Shahlo, M., & Aziza, T. (2023). External Labor Migration And Informal Employment: Situation, Problems And Their Causes. *European Journal Of Business Startups And Open Society*, 3(12), 45-50.

4. Gulchehra, N. (2020). The Importance Of Sustainable And Educational Tourism In The International Pandemic Period (On The Example Of UwtO And Uzbekistan). *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 1(1).

5. Niyozova, I. (2021). Approaches Aimed At Ensuring A High Quality Of Education In The Training Of Economists. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 8(8).

6. Muhammedrisaevna, T. M. S., & Sadikovna, S. M. (2022). Development Trends In Marketing Communications In 2020-2022. *European Multidisciplinary Journal Of Modern Science*, 4, 819-822.

7. Muhammedrizaevna, T. M., Khakimovna, U. M., Abdullayevna, K. Z., & Bayazovna, G. N. The Role Of Using Innovations In Improving The Competitiveness Of Goods. *Gwalior Management Academy*, 11.

8. Aminova, N. B. (2023). Conditions And Factors Of Logistics Infrastructure Development In Uzbekistan. *Studies In Economics And Education In The Modern World*, 2(10).

9. Zebiniso, N. Z., & Maftuna, N. (2023). Cluster Approach In Tourism. *European Journal Of Business Startups And Open Society*, 3(12), 55-57.

10. Mukhamedova, D., Abdullajanova, D., Tukhtabekov, K., Fuzailova, G., Babadjanova, S., & Rahmonova, Z. (2019). The Main Directions Of Accounting Socio-Psychological Characteristics Of The Manager Of Education In The Process Of Optimizing Management Activities In Uzbekistan. *Journal Of Advanced Research In Dynamical And Control Systems*, 11(10 Special Issue), 1035-1038.

11. Усманова, А. (2020). Prospects For Development Of Rural Tourism In Uzbekistan. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 4(4).

12. Abdulloyev, A. (2021). Innovative Factors For Agriculture Development. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 8(8).

13. Kayimova, Z. A., & Bakayeva, M. A. (2022). The Role Of Islamic Finance In The Capital Market In Uzbekistan. *European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 2(1), 370-373.
14. Sayfullayeva, M. S. (2022). Directions For The Practice Of Sustainable Tourism For Ecotourism Destinations In Uzbekistan. *American Journal Of Economics And Business Management*, 5(12), 98-109.
15. Qulliyev, O., & Abduqahhorov, B. (2020). Economic Globalization. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Vuxdu. Uz)*, 2(2).
16. Sh, B. D., & Aminova, N. B. (2021). The Role Of Tourism Companies In The World Community: Their Logistics Processes. *International Journal Of Development And Public Policy*, 1(5), 137-141.
17. Giyazova, N. B., & Teacher, G. N. B. S. Impact Of Strategic Marketing On Enterprise Competitiveness.
18. Narzullayeva, G., & Dehkonov, B. (2015). The Opportunities Of Development Foreign Economic Activity In Bukhara Region. *Scientific Enquiry In The Contemporary World: Theoretical Basics And Innovative Approach [L 26]*, 1, 26-28.
19. Igamova, S. (2022). Directions Of Activation Of Innovative Activities At Building Materials Enterprises. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Vuxdu. Uz)*, 22(22).
20. Rustamovich, K. M. (2023). The Impact Of Using Key Performance Indicators On The Development Of Higher Education Institutions. *Excellencia: International Multi-Disciplinary Journal Of Education (2994-9521)*, 1(5), 385-390.
21. Khalimova, N. J., & Dzhafarova, N. A. (2021). Switzerland As The Home Of Hospitality Education. *European Research: Innovation In Science, Education And Technology*, 29-32.

22. Dustova, A. K. (2023). Features Of Esg Management Development In Uzbekistan. *Educational Research In Universal Sciences*, 2(17), 53-57.

23. Dilafiruz, N. (2020). Importance Of Foreign Investments In The Development Of The Digital Economy: Narzieva Dm International Article. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 1(1).

24. Junaydullaevich, A. A., & Jamshedovna, Q. H. (2021). Organizational And Economic Mechanisms For The Development Of Competitive Agricultural Production On The Basis Of Cooperative Relations. *Academic Journal Of Digital Economics And Stability*, 6, 142-147.

25. Urakova, M. H., & Tairova, M. M. (2021). Practical Recommendations For The Implementation Of Auditing Activities Based On The Existing Document Documents" Professional Standard" Auditor". *World Economics And Finance Bulletin*, 2(2), 23-27.

